

TEACHER'S WORKLOAD AND WELL-BEING AND THEIR IMPLICATION TO LEARNERS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT: *The workloads and well-being of the teachers are important factors to consider when working towards achieving our educational goals. In this study, we investigated the teachers' workloads and well-being and explored their relationships with the academic performance of the students. High school teachers from three divisions in Northern Mindanao, Philippines participated in a survey on the extent of their workloads and their workplace well-being. Majority of the respondents reported moderate to heavy workloads. They also responded positively in all three domains of well-being considered in this study. Comparing the teachers' responses with the National Achievement Test (NAT) scores of their students reveals no significant relationships. The results suggest that there is no direct link between the teachers' workloads and well-being and their students' academic performance. However, the moderate to heavy workloads reported by the respondents reverberate a pressing issue in the educational workforce. Furthermore, based on the responses, among the three domains of well-being, the environmental domain scores the lowest. Thus, for policymakers and school administrators, we recommend considering the work environment and the workloads of the teachers in adopting policies and measures relevant to the teacher working conditions in order to address the issues related to them.*

Keywords: Teacher's well-being, workload, teachers' ancillary assignments, academic performance

1. INTRODUCTION

A major goal of the academe is to optimize learning, as indicated by the ever growing literature on the factors affecting students' academic performance. In the Philippines, the National Achievement Test (NAT) is conducted regularly to closely monitor the academic performances of the students and to determine if the students are meeting the learning standards (DepEd Memorandum No. 68, s. 2018). The data generated from this standardized test are utilized by the stakeholders who seek to contribute to the overall improvement of the quality of education. The current system champions student-centered learning but the teachers still remain a dominant element in the education of the students [1]. A student's academic performance is a product of many factors within and out of the school. Among school-related factors, teachers matter the most [2]. Teachers affect student performances and can influence long-term outcomes such as career paths and economic status [3, 4].

As an important stakeholder in education, the teachers have to be capacitated to be more efficient, updated, and effective because this will ensure that they will have the skill set that matches the needs of the dynamic world and to help achieve our goals of building an equitable nation [5]. The teacher's performance is a crucial element in attaining the academic goals and is itself affected by many factors which may have direct implications to the learner's academic performance.

In the Philippine educational system, the workload of the teachers is a pressing issue. On top of the main job as facilitator of learning, the teacher also has different tasks to fulfill as part of the workload. The Philippine Institute for Developmental Studies (PIDS) recommended that the Department of Education (DepEd) needs to reassess their human resources so as to address the issues on teacher workloads which is a major step towards quality education [6]. Studies conducted in many countries across different cultural contexts confirm connections between workload and the performance level of teachers [7, 8, 9, 10, 11]. Furthermore, teachers who have heavy workloads have a

hard time pursuing their professional development [10] and are prone to exhaustion and high levels of stress which may lead to burnout and sickness, thereby negatively affecting their performance [9, 11, 12, 13, 14].

In addition, teachers' workloads influence their motivation to be efficient in their job. Teachers are most likely to be less motivated and leave the profession early if the workload becomes burdensome [15]. Teaching can be a rewarding profession but, due to the complex nature of the job, stress and dissatisfaction are recurring issues resulting in teachers leaving the profession within the first few years of service [16]. Workload has been found to affect well-being as well [13, 9].

Recent advances in behavioral sciences contribute much to the increasing awareness of the emotional and mental issues relevant to employment as more institutions today recognize the importance of the individual's well-being and its role in the performance of duties of employees [5, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21]. Well-being is the experience of health, happiness, and prosperity [22]. For teachers, it relates to the satisfaction of doing their job as educators, stress-free working environment, and healthy relationship with the stakeholders [21]. Teachers' well-being affects their work engagement, willingness to stay in the profession, and the quality of teaching [18].

Moreover, the school itself is an organization within a complex ecosystem of organizations and has certain objectives which it seeks to achieve. The organizational climate, which refers to the working conditions among heads and teachers, must be considered as a determinant of how effectively the school can achieve its goals. Teachers who are in an open school climate, regularly supervised, and whose needs are well provided, including better infrastructure and facilities, tend to exhibit high levels of job performance [23, 24, 25]. Thus, the leadership from the national government down to the local government units, divisions, and principals must provide the necessary support and facilities to the teachers.

The teachers are the key to achieving the academe’s goal in advancing the learners to higher standards of performance. Therefore, quality education needs well performing and motivated teachers. Furthermore, the demands of the society are constantly changing and the teachers’ well-being, workloads and related factors thereof are areas requiring more attention. In this paper, we report on the workload and well-being of high school teachers from three divisions in Northern Mindanao and their possible connections to the academic performances of their students.

2. METHODOLOGY

Respondents and Gathering of Data

The respondents were high school teachers from the DepEd Divisions of Misamis Oriental (N=562), Cagayan de Oro City (N=57), and El Salvador City (N=23). In generating the data, two survey instruments were utilized: a researcher-made questionnaire for the teacher profile-related data and an adopted questionnaire for the well-being [26]. The instruments were evaluated and validated by experts and have a reliability coefficient of 0.93 by Chronbach alpha.

When the survey was conducted, during the 4th quarter of 2020, Proclamation No. 922 s.2020 was in full effect to curb the spread of the Covid-19. Movement within population centers and provincial borders was restricted which limits our contact with the respondents and only the available responses were treated as data and analyzed. The respondents were also assured of the confidentiality of their responses. The survey was voluntary and conducted with permission from the Department of Education - Divisions of Misamis Oriental, Cagayan de Oro City, and El Salvador City.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Workload

Actual Teaching Load (ATL) refers to the hours of teacher-student contact in the classroom. One hour of contact is equivalent to 1 ATL. Ancillary/Administrative Assignment (AAA) refers to the teacher’s assignments, tasks, and services on top of the teaching job (RA 4670; DepEd Memo 291 s.2008). Ancillary assignments are grouped into three categories: *Heavy* if an assignment may need at least 5 hours a week of the teacher’s time, *Moderate* if 1-4 hours a week, and *Light* when the assignment is performed monthly. A heavy assignment is equivalent to 1 teaching load, 0.5 for moderate assignments, and 0.25 for light assignments [27]. The total workload per day is the sum of ATL, AAA, and two hours of preparation of lessons and checking of students’ outputs. The hours of services rendered beyond the daily 8-hour duty are considered an overload. For example, if a teacher has an ATL of 6 hours and is an adviser (an ancillary with an equivalent of 1 teaching load [27]), then her weekly overload is 5 hours.

The majority of the respondents from the divisions of Misamis Oriental and Cagayan de Oro reported having thirty (30) hours of weekly teaching load while the majority of the respondents from El Salvador reported a weekly teaching load of 25 hours (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. Respondents’ Weekly Teaching Loads in Misamis Oriental, Cagayan de Oro, and El Salvador

A 30-hours weekly teaching load means that a teacher spends 6 hours of actual teaching per day. The respondents from the three divisions carry ancillary loads equivalent to around 5 to 6 hours of teaching loads (Table 1).

Table 1. Average weekly workload and overload

	Teaching Load	Ancillary	Overload
Misamis Oriental (N = 562)	24.02	6.77	0.79
Cagayan de Oro (N = 57)	25.53	7.57	3.09
El Salvador (N = 23)	23.26	5.98	-0.76

The respondents from Cagayan de Oro reported the most amount of overload at around 3.09 followed by teachers from Misamis Oriental at 0.79. Respondents from El Salvador enjoyed the lightest overload at -0.76. A negative overload suggests that the teachers have available time for other school related activities aside from teaching, preparations, and ancillary tasks.

Table 2 ranks the most common ancillary assignments and the percentages of the respondents assigned to the ancillary assignments are shown.

Table 2. Common Ancillaries Among the Respondents

Ancillary Assignments	Percentage (%) of the Respondents	Rank
Class Adviser	72.43	1
Subject Area Coordinator	14.49	2
Grade Level Coordinator	11.68	3
Scouting Coordinator	5.76	4
ICT Coordinator	7.17	5
BAC Secretariat	7.01	6
Guidance Coordinator	4.67	8
Property Custodian	4.52	7
LIS/BEIS Coordinator	4.05	9
Sports Coordinator	2.80	10

Accordingly, 72.43% of the respondents were class advisers, 14.49% were subject area coordinators, and 11.68% were grade level coordinators, and so on. A teacher may be assigned to more than one ancillary. For example, a class adviser may also be a sports coordinator at the same time.

Well-Being of Teachers

Well-being can be described as having a positive outlook of life and satisfaction [28, 29]. Environmental domain of well-being refers to the well-being of teachers in relation to their

environmental conditions, physical surroundings, and access to resources. Communal domain relates well-being with the professional community and relationships within the working environment. And personal domain refers to the teachers' well-being in relation to their personal fulfillment, satisfaction, and quality of life [30, 31].

Table 3. Well-Being of Teachers in 3 Domains

Domain	Response	Misamis Oriental	Cagayan de Oro	El Salvador
Environmental	<i>Strongly Agree</i>	25%	15%	19%
	<i>Agree</i>	56%	52%	57%
	<i>Slightly Agree</i>	19%	33%	24%
Communal	<i>Strongly Agree</i>	47%	35%	52%
	<i>Agree</i>	53%	62%	48%
	<i>Slightly Agree</i>	10%	13%	10%
Personal	<i>Strongly Agree</i>	34%	26%	24%
	<i>Agree</i>	55%	61%	57%
	<i>Slightly Agree</i>	16%	13%	19%

The respondents from all of the three divisions responded positively to the survey on well-being, agreeing to most items under the three domains (Table 3). The negative responses are negligible. The majority positive responses indicate that in general, the respondents feel satisfied, safe, and accepted in their schools in their respective environments, communities, and with the people they usually interact with. However, the environmental domain of well-being received the most responses in the *slightly agree* and the least in the *strongly agree* from the respondents from the three divisions.

National Achievement Test Scores

Regarding the academic performances of the high school students from the three divisions, we used the National Achievement Test (NAT) scores as objective measures of their performances. Schools use NAT results to determine whether the students achieved the performance standards specified in the curriculum. The overall performance of a group of students from a school is shown as the mean percentage score (MPS). These scores are available, upon request, in the DepEd division offices.

Relationship between the Workload and Well-being and the NAT Scores

In determining the relationship between the workload and NAT scores, the workloads of the teachers from a school were compared with the school's latest MPS report available in the 4th quarter of 2020. Investigation of the relationship between the teachers' workloads and the NAT MPS of the schools using correlation and regression reveals no significant relationship between the two with weak correlations (Tables 4 and 5).

Table 4. Correlations (Workload-NAT MPS)

		NATMPS
Pearson Correlation	Workload	-.035
Sig. (1-tailed)	Workload	.459

Table 5. Regression – Workload and NAT MPS

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. The error of the Estimate
1	.035 ^a	.001	-.110	10.35975

On average, the respondents in Misamis Oriental spent around 7.5 hours weekly in teaching preparations and around 3.5 hours in ancillary assignments. Respondents from Cagayan de Oro also spent around 7.5 hours for their teaching preparations and 3.5 hours in ancillary assignments. El Salvador respondents, on the other hand, spent a little less at around 5.5 hours weekly for teaching preparations and 3.5 hours in ancillary assignments (Table 6). The ancillary assignments are flexible in their schedules and the time and effort needed to accomplish the ancillaries depend on the situation. For example, *Gender and Development (GAD) Coordinator* is an ancillary worth 0.25 teaching loads on paper but the task may take more time to accomplish during the month of March which is designated as the National Women's Month (Proclamation No. 227 s.1988).

Table 6. Hours Spent Weekly in Preparations and Ancillary

	Misamis Oriental	Cagayan de Oro	El Salvador
Weekly Preparations	7.50	7.50	5.50
Weekly Ancillary	3.50	3.50	3.50

An investigation of the relationship between the self-reported total time spent on ancillary assignments and preparations, and NAT MPS reveals no significant relationship between the two (Tables 7 and 8).

Table 7. Correlations (Total Time Spent Weekly in Preparations and Ancillary and NAT MPS)

		NAT MPS
Pearson Correlation	Total Time Spent Weekly	.022
Sig. (1-tailed)	Total Time Spent Weekly	.474

Table 8. Regression - Total Time Spent Weekly in Preparations and Ancillary and NAT MPS

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
.022 ^a	.000	-.111

An analysis of the relationship between the well-being and the NAT MPS reveals no significant relationship between them (Tables 9 and 10), implying that the teachers' well-being has no direct effect on the NAT performance of the students.

All in all, the results show that teacher workload and well-being are not good predictors for National Achievement Test results.

Table 9. Correlation (All Variables)

		NAT MPS
Pearson Correlation	Environmental Wellbeing	.255
	Communal WellBeing	-.081
	Personal WellBeing	.296
Sig. (1-tailed)	Environmental Wellbeing	.225
	Communal WellBeing	.407
	Personal WellBeing	.189

Table 10. Regression - Overall Well-being and NAT MPS

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
.415	.172	-.183

The NAT results may be a function of factors apart from the teacher workload and well-being.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The respondents from the three divisions reported having moderate to heavy workloads with some respondents reporting two or more ancillaries. This echoes a major issue in the workloads of teachers in the Philippines [6]. The

assignment of workloads to the teachers must be reviewed to promote a healthy balance in the hours spent for job-related functions, professional development, and their personal lives. With regards to the overall well-being of the teachers, it is generally positive. However, the environmental aspect of well-being which encompasses the immediate surroundings and access to resources, scores the lowest among the three domains, having the most *Slightly Agree* responses and the least *Strongly Agree* responses. Policies and measures regarding the school's immediate environment and accessibility to basic services may be adopted by the school heads, division offices and the local government units to address the needs of the teachers for a safer and more conducive work environment.

It is also found that well-being and workload do not directly determine NAT results. This suggests that the well-being and workload of the teachers have negligible effects on the students' academic performance which seems to defy the connections teacher's workload and well-being to teacher performance and teacher performance to student's performance as found in many studies. Thus, we recommend exploring other possible mediating factors in future investigations.

Although the NAT scores offer a general view of the students' academic performances, they do not reflect thorough information of their actual performances which can be obtained from sources such as classroom outputs, involvement in the community, and changes in their behaviors and attitudes. We recommend that a more comprehensive picture of students' performance be adopted in further investigations.

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